

FATIGUE STRENGTH PREDICTION OF BOLTED JOINT STRUCTURES OF CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED POLYMER COMPOSITE BASED ON THE MICROMECHANICS

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, the theory of micro-mechanics of failure (MMF) is extended to analyze the fatigue progressive failure and predict the strength for the bolted joint structures of carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) composite. The MMF approach includes the material strength characterization and structure strength design for the CFRP structures. The material strength characterization includes macro-mechanics experiments for the unidirectional laminates, micro-mechanics analysis and MMF critical parameters extraction. The structure strength design includes modelling of a specific structure, macroscopic stress analysis, microscopic stress magnification, constituents' failure judgments, material properties degradation and crack propagation in the structures. The feature of the approach is that the material properties degradation of each element in each calculation step is determined by the constituents' failure judged physically by the MMF parameters of the key points in the micro-mechanics model. The structure strength design is realized by developing the user defined material (UMAT) subroutine with FORTRAN scripts on the ABAQUS platform. The evolution of initial failure and progressive failure of the double-bolt double shear lap joint of the UTS50/E51 laminate under the static loading and the fatigue loading, respectively, is analyzed in detail by using the MMF approach. Based on the MMF approach, the fatigue tensile loading failure mechanism for the UTS50/E51 double-bolt joints structures and its *S-N* curves is analyzed, and a comparison with the test results is conducted.

1 INTRODUCTION

The carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) have many excellent features, such as higher strength and specific stiffness, strong design ability, good fatigue properties, corrosion resistance and so on, so it is widely used in aviation, aerospace and other advanced fields. The mechanical joint structure is the key factor for applying the CFRP materials to the model industries because the joints are the potential weaknesses of the composite structures. In recent years, the composite bolted structures are widely investigated in many aspects^[1-9], such as the failure analysis, load distribution, fatigue lifespan and joint strength. In order to guarantee the security of the CFRP composite structure in use, it is necessary to develop the accurate strength theories.

Currently, the traditional macro strength theory is still the widely used theory for composite structures, like the Tsai-Wu^[10], Hashin^[11] and Puck^[12] theory. These theories are mainly based on the mathematic approximation formulas and the error will be relatively big in practical situations. Where, the Tsai-Wu theory fails to specify the failure mechanism of damage. Hashin and Park considered the constituent failure mechanism, but those failure criteria are not calculated in micro-level. In essence, they also belong to the macro analysis. In order to overcome the deficiencies of the macro theories, it is imperative to build a real physically strength theory for composite materials, which will have great importance in the design and application of the CFRP composites.

The micro-mechanics of failure (MMF) proposed by Ha et al^[13] is a real physics-based strength theory for strength prediction of the structures made of carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) laminates, in which the initial failure of constituents is analyzed in micro-level with the interactive failure criteria. In their research, the square or hexagonal unit cell model applied with the loads, corresponding to the stress states in macro-level, at the boundaries were used to look insight into the

stresses in the fibre and matrix in micro-level. Based on the interactive MMF, both transverse tensile and compressive failure of the Graphite/Epoxy were analyzed in that paper. In this way, the strength and failure modes of laminate with multidirectional stacking sequence have been predicted. These predictions are compared with predictions from other widely used failure criteria as well as experimental data, good agreement was confirmed. However, the large amount of iterative calculation for the extraction of the MMF critical parameters using the interactive failure criteria lowers the computational efficiency and has a poor convergence performance. Therefore, a simple and reliable MMF failure criterion that can increase computational efficiency and improve the convergence is necessary.

This paper establishes the MMF approach which extends MMF theory to analyze the fatigue progressive failure and conduct the strength prediction for the bolted joint structures of the UTS50/E51 CFRP composites. The MMF approach includes the material strength characterization and structure strength prediction for the CFRP structures. The material strength characterization includes macro-mechanics experiments, micro-mechanics analysis and MMF critical parameters extraction. The structure strength design includes modelling of a specific structure, macroscopic stress analysis, microscopic stress amplification, constituents' failure judgments, material properties degradation and crack propagation in the structures. The structure strength prediction is realized by developing the user defined material (UMAT) subroutine with FORTRAN scripts on the ABAQUS platform. Micro-scale stress of the constituents is visualized for detailed analysis. The progressive failure and the strengths of the double-bolt double shear lap joint of the UTS50/E51 laminate under the static loading and the fatigue loading, respectively, are analyzed in details by using the MMF approach. Finally, the analysis accuracy of the MMF approach is compared with that of the classical Tsai-Wu and Hashin theories.

2 THE MICROMECHANICS-BASED STRENGTH THEORY FOR COMPOSITES

2.1 Micro-mechanics of failure criteria

In the MMF theory, the constituent strength is characterized by four MMF critical parameters, including the fibre tensile strength T_f , the fiber compressive strength C_f , the matrix tensile strength T_m , and the matrix compressive strength C_m . T_f and C_f are used to judge the failure of fiber under tensile and compressive loading, respectively. T_m and C_m are used to judge the failure of matrix under tensile and compressive loading, respectively. The calculations of the four characteristic values are shown as formula (1).

$$\begin{cases} T_f = \sigma_1^f, (\sigma_1^f > 0) \\ C_f = \sigma_{eq}^f, (\sigma_1^f < 0) \\ T_m = I_1^m \\ C_m = \sigma_{eq}^m \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Where the material axes 123 are used as coordinate direction. σ_1 is the stress of fiber direction, I_1 is the first stress invariant and σ_{eq} is the equivalent stress. The superscript/subscript f and m represent the fiber and matrix respectively.

It is necessary to point out that, this paper uses the none-interactive MMF failure criteria. The fiber tensile strength is extracted by using the maximum stress along the fiber length direction because fibers only present high rigidity in the longitudinal direction and the rigidities in other directions are very low. So it can be described as the maximum strength of fiber direction. The fiber compressive strength is described by the equivalent stress on the fiber. As to the failure of the matrix, Gosse and Christensen^[14] proposed the strain invariant failure theory to describe the strength of matrix, the first invariant of strain J_1 and the equivalent strain ε_{eq} are used to characterize the tensile strength and compressive strength of matrix respectively, because J_1 is suitable to judge the failure due to the volume increase while ε_{eq} is suitable to judge matrix failure due to the shearing deformation. This paper uses the first stress invariant I_1 and the equivalent stress σ_{eq} which correspond to J_1 and ε_{eq} , to describe the tensile strength and compressive strength of matrix, respectively.

As it can be seen from formula (2), once the value of k reaches to 1, the material is suffered to the corresponding mode of damage. Therefore, in the MMF theory, the MMF critical parameters of the

constituents are the key indexes for analyzing the structure strength of the laminates. Hence, to accurately predict the strengths of the laminate structures, it is necessary to accurately calculate the values of the four MMF critical parameters of T_f , C_f , T_m and C_m .

$$k = \max[k_{T,f}, k_{C,f}, k_{T,m}, k_{C,m}]$$

$$k_{T,f} = \max(\sigma_1^{f,1}/T_f, \dots, \sigma_1^{f,i}/T_f, \dots, \sigma_1^{f,n_1}/T_f)$$

$$k_{C,f} = \max(\sigma_{eq}^{f,1}/C_f, \dots, \sigma_{eq}^{f,i}/C_f, \dots, \sigma_{eq}^{f,n_1}/C_f) \quad (2)$$

$$k_{T,m} = \max(I_1^{m,1}/T_m, \dots, I_1^{m,j}/T_m, \dots, I_1^{m,n_2}/T_m)$$

$$k_{C,m} = \max(\sigma_{eq}^{m,1}/C_m, \dots, \sigma_{eq}^{m,j}/C_m, \dots, \sigma_{eq}^{m,n_2}/C_m)$$

Where k without subscript means the failure index of the element, $k_{T,f}$ and $k_{C,f}$ are the fiber tensile failure index and fiber compressive failure index, respectively; $k_{T,m}$ and $k_{C,m}$ are the matrix tensile failure index and matrix compressive failure index, respectively; $i=1\dots n_1, j=1\dots n_2, n_1, n_2$ represent the total numbers of the key points in the fiber and the matrix, respectively.

When the element within the structure fails, an action against the material property degradation should be performed according to the failure mechanism, which needs to introduce the constituent damage factors. The definitions of the constituent damage factors are shown in formula (3) to formula (6).

Tensile fiber failure ($\sigma_1^f > 0$)
If $k_{T,f} \geq 1$, then $d_f = 0.99$ (3)

Compressive fiber failure ($\sigma_1^f < 0$)
If $k_{C,f} \geq 1$, then $d_f = 0.99$ (4)

Tensile matrix failure
If $k_{T,m} \geq 1$, then $d_m = 0.99$ (5)

Compressive matrix failure
If $k_{C,m} \geq 1$, then $d_m = 0.99$ (6)

Where d_f is the fiber damage parameter; d_m is the matrix damage parameter.

The laminate gradual failure analysis is conducted by calculating the constituent failure indexes of each element to adjust the values of its constituent damage factors, thus a material reasonable performance degradation scheme can be applied to each element of the structure. With the loads increasing, the failure indexes, damage factors and the distribution of stresses are updating constantly until the laminates fails completely. The specific implementation method is described in chapter 4.1.

2.2 Macro-micro mechanics analysis method of the composite materials

The unit cell model with the face-centered array distribution of carbon fibers is constructed, shown in Figure 1, to analyze the stresses of fiber and matrix in micro-level by FEM using ANSYS code. This unit cell model is applied with prescribed loads of average unit stress in one of three normal stresses and one of three shear stresses as well as one case with thermal load of unit temperature in the unit cell model. The stress extractions of the key points and the characterization method for the laminate constituent strengths, these are introduced in paper^[15] elaborately. This paper will not give further description.

Figure 1: The unit cell model with the face-centered array distribution of carbon fibres and location of key points for the extraction of stress amplification factors within unit cell.

The stresses of laminate are converted to the stresses of fiber and matrix at micro level using the stress amplification factors. The output result of macro stresses from the finite element analysis at macro-level or from classical laminated plate theory is amplified through these amplification factors

before failure analysis. The key point among these key points is identified by comparing the values of strength ratio using failure criterion with the MMF critical parameters of the constituents. The stresses modification from the macro-level to the micro level is carried out with the expression using the obtained stress amplification factors.

The conversion formula between the micro-stresses and the macro-stresses of the unidirectional layer continuous fiber reinforced composites is shown as formula (7):

$$\begin{pmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \sigma_3 \\ \tau_{12} \\ \tau_{13} \\ \tau_{23} \end{pmatrix}^{(i)} = \begin{bmatrix} M_{11} & M_{12} & M_{13} & M_{14} & M_{15} & M_{16} \\ M_{21} & M_{22} & M_{23} & M_{24} & M_{25} & M_{26} \\ M_{31} & M_{32} & M_{33} & M_{34} & M_{35} & M_{36} \\ M_{41} & M_{42} & M_{43} & M_{44} & M_{45} & M_{46} \\ M_{51} & M_{52} & M_{53} & M_{54} & M_{55} & M_{56} \\ M_{61} & M_{62} & M_{63} & M_{64} & M_{65} & M_{66} \end{bmatrix}^{(i)} \begin{pmatrix} \bar{\sigma}_1 \\ \bar{\sigma}_2 \\ \bar{\sigma}_3 \\ \bar{\tau}_{12} \\ \bar{\tau}_{13} \\ \bar{\tau}_{23} \end{pmatrix}_{\text{mech}} + \begin{pmatrix} A_1 \\ A_2 \\ A_3 \\ A_4 \\ A_5 \\ A_6 \end{pmatrix}_{\sigma} \Delta T \quad (7)$$

where σ_i is the micro-stress of the key pint i in fibre or matrix, $\bar{\sigma}_i$ is the macro-stress in CFRP laminate, ΔT is the temperature difference between environment temperature and the curing temperature, $M_{\sigma}^{(i)}$ is the stress amplification factors of the key point i either in fiber or matrix matrix, $A_{\sigma}^{(i)}$ is the thermal stress amplification factors for the key point i .

3. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

3.1 Materials and specimens

The stacking sequences of the tested CFRP laminates are $[0]_{10}$, $[90]_{20}$, $[45/-45]_{5s}$, $[45/0/-45/90]_{4s}$ of UTS50/E51, which consists of UTS50 carbon fiber and E51 epoxy resin. The volume fraction of the fiber is approximately 0.56. The experimental scheme for the unidirectional laminates and the sizes of its specimens are shown in Table 1. The bolted joint structure uses the laminates with a stacking-sequence of $[45/0/-45/90]_{4s}$ and a 6mm diameter bolt of stainless steel 304. The laminates are 135mm long and 36mm wide, and the distance between the hole centre and the free end is 18mm, as shown in Figure 2. All the laminates were made by hot pressing technique. The curing procedure includes 80 °C for 30 min, and subsequent 130 °C for 60min under pressure of 5MPa. The laminates will be taken out after the temperature cools down to the room temperature.

Test type	Stacking sequence	Specimen size (mm) (L×W×H)
In-plane shear	$[45/-45]_{5s}$	200×15×2
Longitudinal tensile	$[0]_{10}$	200×12.5×1
Longitudinal compressive	$[0]_{20}$	78×10×2
Transverse tensile	$[90]_{20}$	200×15×2
Transverse compressive	$[90]_{20}$	78×10×2

Table 1: Experimental scheme and specimen size of the laminates UTS50/E51

Figure 2: The bolted joints structure specimen with stacking sequence $[45/0/-45/90]_{4s}$ and boundary conditions.

3.2 Static testing

The tensile test of the unidirectional laminates was carried out according to the ISO527 standard,

and the tensile strains of the specimens during loading process of loading were measured. The three point bending method was used to test the longitudinal compressive strength according to ISO14125 standards, and the transverse compression test was implemented according to ISO14126 standard. The static tensile loading experiment was carried out according the ASTM D5961/65961M-05 method. Every experiment was repeated for 5 times and the mean value was calculated out. All the static experiments were performed under the electronic universal experiment machine controlled by the INSTRON1195 with a 10kN loading unit which is controlled by a microcomputer.

Through the experiment, the longitudinal tensile strength X , the longitudinal compressive strength X' , the transverse tensile strength Y , the transverse compressive strength Y' and the shearing strength S of the UTS50/E51 unidirectional laminates were obtained, shown in Table 2. The properties of the laminates, the UTS50 fiber and the E51 matrix are shown in Table 3. The critical MMF parameters of the UTS50 fiber and the E51 matrix are shown in table 4. The static tensile loading strength of the bolted joints structure is 17.8KN.

Strength parameters	Average strength (MPa)
Longitudinal tensile strength X	2100
Longitudinal compressive strength X'	1932
Transverse tensile strength Y	54
Transverse compressive strength Y'	179
Shear strength S	140

Table 2: The uniaxial strength of the unidirectional laminates for UTS50/E51

Material properties	Ply	Fiber	Matrix
Fiber volume fraction V_f	0.56	1.0	0.0
Longitudinal modulus E_1 (GPa)	136	240	3.0
Transverse modulus $E_2 = E_3$ (GPa)	10	42	3.0
Shear modulus $G_{12} = G_{13}$ (GPa)	4.7	23	1.06
Shear modulus G_{23} (GPa)	3.2	12	1.09
Poisson's ratios $\mu_{12} = \mu_{13}$	0.35	0.33	0.38
Poisson's ratio μ_{23}	0.56	0.71	0.38
Longitudinal coefficient of thermal expansion α_1 (K^{-1})	-0.34×10^{-6}	-0.87×10^{-6}	6.0×10^{-5}
Transverse coefficient of thermal expansion $\alpha_2 = \alpha_3$ (K^{-1})	75×10^{-6}	40×10^{-6}	6.0×10^{-5}

Table 3: Material properties of the unidirectional laminates for UTS50/E51

Strength parameters	Values (MPa)
Fiber tensile strength T_f	3710
Fiber compression strength C_f	3430
Matrix tensile strength T_m	155
Matrix compression strength C_m	207

Table 4: The MMF critical parameters of UTS50/E51

3.3 Fatigue testing

The fatigue longitudinal and transverse tensile experiments of the unidirectional laminates were carried out according to the SACMA 4R-94 standard. The transverse compressive experiment was carried out according to the SACMA 1R-94 standard. The longitudinal three-point bending experiment was carried out according to the ISO 14125 standard. The fatigue tensile experiment of the bolted joint structure was carried out according to the ASTM STP 749 method. The applied bolt torque was 10 N•m.

For all the fatigue experiments, the stress ratio R was 0.05 and the frequency was 10Hz. When the specimens broke completely or the cycle number reached to 106, the experiment was stopped manually. All the experiments were performed on the universal electronic experiment machine, the

model of which is MTS 858 MINI BIONIX II.

Though the fatigue test of the UTS50/E51 unidirectional laminates, the $S-N$ curves of the longitudinal tensile fatigue, longitudinal compressive fatigue, the transverse tensile fatigue and the transverse compressive fatigue were obtained respectively, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: The $S-N$ curves for (a) longitudinal fatigue loading tension, (b) longitudinal fatigue loading compressive, (c) transverse fatigue loading tension, (d) transverse fatigue loading compressive of UTS50/E51 unidirectional laminates.

4 THE NUMERICAL ANALYSIS MODEL

4.1 Damage model derivation

The composite damage analysis plays an important role in the analysis of the properties of the laminate structures. Kachanov^[16] pointed that the effect of the material damage on the whole material properties can be realized by lowering the stiffness matrix of the material in the stress updating process. According to the material damage strength calculation model proposed by McCarthy^[17] and combined with the MMF theory, this paper establishes a new progressive failure analysis model based on the MMF theory. As the CFRP laminates present the elastic-brittle behaviours under stresses, there is no obvious plastic deformation when failure happens. Therefore, the plastic behaviours of this material can be ignored in model building. The stiffness matrix of the material in the progressive failure model is shown as formula (8):

$$[C]_{ijkl} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & C_{22} & C_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & C_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & \text{symm} & & C_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ & & & & C_{55} & 0 \\ & & & & & C_{66} \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

Where

$$\begin{aligned}
C_{11} &= E_1(1-d_f)[1-(1-d_m)^2v_{23}^2]/A \\
C_{22} &= E_2(1-d_m)[1-(1-d_m)(1-d_f)v_{13}v_{31}]/A \\
C_{33} &= E_2(1-d_m)[1-(1-d_m)(1-d_f)v_{12}v_{21}]/A \\
C_{12} &= E_2(1-d_m)(1-d_f)[(1-d_m)v_{13}v_{23} + v_{12}]/A \\
C_{13} &= E_2(1-d_m)(1-d_f)[(1-d_m)v_{12}v_{23} + v_{13}]/A \\
C_{23} &= E_2(1-d_m)^2[v_{23}^2 + (1-d_f)v_{12}v_{31}]/A \\
C_{44} &= G_{12}(1-d_m)(1-d_f) \\
C_{55} &= G_{13}(1-d_m)(1-d_f) \\
C_{66} &= G_{23}(1-d_m)(1-d_f) \\
A &= 1-(1-d_m)(1-d_f)v_{12}v_{21} - (1-d_m)^2v_{23}v_{32} \\
&\quad - (1-d_m)(1-d_f)v_{13}v_{31} - 2(1-d_m)^2(1-d_f)v_{12}v_{31}v_{23}
\end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

As the continuous fibre reinforced composites have nonlinear shearing behaviours, this model considers the nonlinear shearing properties of the UTS50/E51 laminates in the process of stress updating, the detailed implementation method is described in paper^[18]. For each loading step, the macroscopic stresses of the element are converted into the micro-stresses of key points in the fibre and matrix, then judge whether or not the failure of the fiber or the matrix happen according to the MMF parameters, then material properties degradation and crack propagation in the structures are performed. All these works are carried out using the user defined material (UMAT) subroutine with Fortran scripts on the ABAQUS platform.

4.2 Geometry model

The bolted joints structure is made of multidirectional quasi-isotropic laminates with a stacking sequence of $[45/0/-45/90]_{4s}$. Each layer of the laminate is 0.1mm and the bolt is regarded as a rigid body in the model. The geometry size of the bolted joint structure and its boundary limitations are shown in Figure 2. The finite element (FEM) mesh of the bolt structure laminate is shown in Figure 4. The FEM element type is the three-dimensional solid element C3D8R, and the analysis is implemented using Python scripts. The implicit solver is used for solution.

Figure 4: Mesh of the FEM model for the laminates of the bolted joints specimen, (a) mesh for the laminates, (b) mesh near the hole.

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Characterization of fatigue strength

The extraction method for the constituent fatigue MMF critical parameters is the same as that of the static loading MMF critical parameters. However, for inputting the macro strength of the unidirectional laminate, it is fatigue strength of the unidirectional laminate that should be used. The fatigue strength of the unidirectional laminate is obtained by the unidirectional laminate fatigue $S-N$ curve (shown in Figure 3) from the experiment.

The fatigue MMF critical parameters $S-N$ curves for the constituents of the UTS50/E51 laminate are obtained through the MMF critical parameters extraction under different fatigue cycle numbers, as shown in Figure 5, which provides basis for characterization of fatigue strength of the UTS50/E51 laminate.

Figure 5: The $S-N$ curve for (a) fiber fatigue loading tension of UTS50, (b) fiber fatigue loading compressive of UTS50, (c) matrix fatigue loading tension of E51, (d) matrix fatigue loading compressive of E51.

5.2 Progressive failure of bolted joint structures under static tensile loading

The static tensile loading strength of the bolted structure is predicted by using the MMF approach. And the prediction result of the MMF approach is compared to that of the Tsai-Wu and the Hashin theories. Figure 6 shows the comparison between the experiments and predictions, of the static tensile load-displacement curves of the UTS50/E51 bolted joint structures with a stacking sequence of $[45/0/-45/90]_{4s}$.

Figure 6: The static tensile load-displacement curves of the bolted joints structure made of UTS50/E51 laminate with stacking sequence $[45/0/-45/90]_{4s}$

As it can be seen from Figure 6, the static tensile loading strength predicted by the MMF approach is 34.6kN, which is most close to the experiment result and the prediction error is 7.2%. The static tensile loading strength predicted by the Hashin theory is 31.1kN and the prediction error is 16.6%. The static tensile loading strength predicted by the Tsai-Wu theory is 24.6kN and the prediction error is up to 34%. In the figure, the static tensile load-displacement curve of the double-bolt double shear lap joint predicted by the MMF approach presents several ups and downs, which indicates the tensile failure of the double-bolt double shear lap joint is a damage accumulating process. Minor constituent failure will not affect the complete strength of the structure and the structure is subjected to complete damage only when it suffers a certain amount of damage. The load-displacement curve predicted by the Hashin theory appears several turns, which indicates the bolted joint structure undergoes failures of a partial of constituents before the final failure and this is in accordance with the MMF approach.

The evolution of the initial failure and progressive failure of the bolted joint structure with a stacking sequence of $[45/0/-45/90]_{4s}$ of the UTS50/E51 laminate under the static tensile loading are analyzed by using the MMF approach. Figure 7 shows the MMF failure index distribution at the final failure, from layer 1 to layer 4, of the middle laminate, of the bolted joint structure with a stacking

sequence of $[45/0/-45/90]_{4s}$. As it can be seen from the figure, at the final failure, all the laminate has failures both in the fiber and the matrix. In terms of the failure modes, by comprehensively superposing the constituent failure mechanism of the layers, it can be seen that the damages of every layer are centralized beneath the first bolt -hole and second bolt -hole. From the fiber failure region of the 0-degree layer, we can see a certain breadth of fiber compression damage appears on the contact area of the bolt and the hole. The damage region exhibits shear damage growing downward. The shear damage of the 0-degree layer not only results in the damage itself but also results in the shear damage downward of other layers. Hence, the final damage mode of the double-bolt double shear lap joint behaves as shearing mode.

Figure 7: The MMF failure indices distribution of first four layer for the final failure of the bolted joints structure made of UTS50/E51 laminate with stacking sequence $[45/0/-45/90]_{4s}$ under static loading tension

The relationships between the failure mechanism and the tensile displacement under the static tensile loading, of all layers of the middle laminate of the UTS50/E51 bolted structure with a stacking sequence of $[45/0/-45/90]_{4s}$ are analyzed by using the MMF approach. Table 5 shows the relationship between the constituent failure mechanism and the displacement of the middle laminate, from layer 1 to layer 4. As it can be seen from the Table 5, the static tensile loading failure of the double-bolt double shear structure starts from the matrix damage of the 90-degree layer and then to the ± 45 -degree layer. The fiber damage starts from the 0-degree layer and then to the ± 45 -degree layer. When the displacement is more than 2.2mm, the double-bolt double lap joint suffers complete damage.

Tensile displacement /mm	45 degree layer		0 degree layer		-45 degree layer		90 degree layer	
	fiber	matrix	fiber	matrix	fiber	matrix	fiber	matrix
0.48-0.61								•
0.62-0.68		•				•		•
0.69-0.74		•	•			•		•
0.75-1.96		•	•	•		•		•
1.97-2.01	•	•	•	•	•	•		•
> 2.2	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•

Note: •- Means damage

Table 5: Constituents failure modes from initial to final failure based on MMF

Figure 8 shows the macro-scale damage appearance of the middle laminate of the bolted joint structure under static tensile loading failure. As it can be seen from the figure, the final damage mode behaves as shearing mode beneath the hole due to the pressure from the bolt. In terms of the failure position and the crack propagation mode, this conclusion is in accordance with the results of the MMF approach, Tsai-Wu theory and the Hashin theory. But it is difficult to analyze the evolution of initial failure mechanism and progressive failure mechanism of the bolted joint structures by experiments.

Because the double shear bolted structure is a joint structure and it is unavailable to observe the status of the middle laminate in real-time and the fixed point or quantitative method can't be used due to the great dispersion of the composite material failure. So this paper does not give the damage mechanism of the bolted structure in experiment.

Figure 8: Macro-scale fractal surface of the bolted joints structure made of UTS50/E51 laminate with stacking sequence $[45/0/-45/90]_{4s}$ at final static tensile loading failure

As it can be seen from the above analysis, by using the MMF approach, the evolution from the initial failure to progressive failure of the bolted joint structure can be accurately analyzed. It is noted that, the displacement of the predicted load-displacement curve is far less than the experimental result. This is resulted by two aspects. First, the UMAT used in this paper has a good performance in analysis accuracy, but requires high convergence, so it can only analyze the small deformation structures; and for the bolt tensile process, only the complete failure near the hole can be analyzed. Second, after the large area near the hole get damage during the tensile process, the structure will not suffer devastating damage quickly. This process will last for a while. Thus, the displacement observed in the experiment will increase greatly. And the strength of the bolted structure almost keeps constant during the process.

5.3 Progressive failure of bolted joint structures under fatigue tensile loading

The fatigue tensile loading progressive failure of the UTS50/E51 bolted joint structure with a stacking sequence of $[45/0/-45/90]_{4s}$ is analyzed by using the MMF approach. Figure 9 shows the fatigue MMF failure indexes distributions of the middle laminate under the 1000 cycles of bolted joint structure fatigue tension, from layer 1 to layer 4, at the final failure. Compared to the static tensile loading MMF failure indexes distributions, the constituents' failure regions of the layers are obviously smaller. Meanwhile, for the failure mechanism of the double-bolt double shear lap joint under the fatigue tensile loading, it is found that the initial failure and the final damage mechanism almost coincide with the static tensile loading failure. The fatigue damage mode of the bolted structure predicted by the MMF approach also behaves as shearing mode.

The damage mode of the bolted structure under the fatigue tensile loading in the experiment is the shear damage, which is in accordance with the damage mode of the static tensile loading failure of the bolted structure. Thus the analysis of the MMF approach is in consistent with the tested result.

5.4 The $S-N$ curves of the bolted joint structures under fatigue tensile loading

Figure 10 is the $S-N$ curves of the bolted joint structures made of UTS50/E51 laminates with a stacking sequence of $[45/0/-45/90]_{4s}$, which is predicted by the MMF approach. As it can be seen from the figure, the $S-N$ curves predicted with the MMF approach, of the bolted joint structures, agree well with the experimental result of the fatigue tension test of the bolted joint structures under the 10^6 cycles, which reflects variation trend of the fatigue tensile strength of the bolted joint structure with the cycles increasing. But with the cycle numbers increasing, there is still deviation between the predicted $S-N$ curves and the experiment results under the 10^5 - 10^6 cycles. This deviation is mainly because the prediction for the structural strength is based on the fatigue MMF critical parameters characterization of the laminates, but the limited unidirectional laminate fatigue experiment constrains the prediction range. So within the prediction range, the deviation increases with the increment of the fatigue tensile cycles. To ensure accuracy of the prediction, the unidirectional laminate fatigue experiment with a larger range is required. In conclusion, the MMF approach is applicable for the

fatigue strength analysis for the CFRP laminate structures, which provides a new thought to predict the fatigue strength of the CFRP laminate structures.

Figure 9: The MMF failure indices distribution of first four layer for the final failure of the bolted joints structure made of UTS50/E51 laminate with stacking sequence $[45/0/-45/90]_{4s}$ under fatigue tensile loading of 1000 cycles

Figure 10: The $S-N$ curves of the bolted joints structure made of UTS50/E51 laminates with stacking sequence $[45/0/-45/90]_{4s}$

9 CONCLUSIONS

- (1) The micro-mechanics of failure (MMF) approach was established for the fatigue progressive failure analysis and strength prediction for the structures made of carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) composite. The progressive failure mechanism and strength of the complicate three-dimensional CFRP structure under either the static loading or the fatigue loading can be analyzed according to the constituents' failure in micro-level.
- (2) The structure strength prediction was realized by developing the user defined material (UMAT) subroutine with FORTRAN scripts on the ABAQUS platform. The material properties degradation analysis method was constructed according to the failure modes of constituents. The material properties of elements were modified dynamically according to the failure modes of the constituents in the damage process.
- (3) Based on the MMF approach, the static tensile loading failure process, failure mechanism and the strength of the UTS50/E51 bolted structure were analyzed. The static tensile loading failure of bolted joint structure starts from the matrix damage of the 90-degree layer and then to the ± 45 -degree layer. The fiber damage starts from the 0-degree layer and then to the ± 45 -degree layer. The predicted failure mode of the bolted structure by the MMF approach behaves as shearing mode. The static tensile loading strength predicted by the MMF approach is 17kN, which is very close to the experimental result, and the prediction error is 4.5%. Compared to traditional strength theories, the MMF approach agrees best with the experimental result.
- (4) Based on the MMF approach, the failure mechanism under fatigue tensile loading for the

UTS50/E51 bolted joints structures and its $S-N$ curves were analyzed and a comparison for the test results was conducted. The result indicates that failure of bolted joint structure under the fatigue tensile loading starts from the matrix damage of the 90-degree layer and the failure mode of the bolted structure also behaves as shearing mode, and this result coincides well with the experiment. The theoretically predicted $S-N$ curves agree well with the tested result.

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